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SOME NUMERICAL MODELLING OF THE SEASONAL STRATIFICATION OF THE GEMLIK BAY, MARMARA SEA, TÜRKIYE

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Abstract

The water exchange between the Aegean Sea and the Black Sea occurs through a two-layer flow system within the Marmara Sea (Chiggiato et al., 2012; Sunar et al., 2022; Yalçın et al., 2017). These layers are typically separated by a pycnocline located at approximately 25 meters depth, which can be disrupted by strong wind-induced recirculation leading to upwelling events (Beşiktepe et al., 1994; Chiggiato et al., 2012; Mutlu et al., 2023). Similar dynamics are observed in the Gemlik Bay, a 35 km long semi-enclosed basin located in the southeastern Marmara Sea. However, current available models are not able to accurately reproduce stratification patterns shown by measured data.

In this study, simulations are conducted using Delft3D, for the period from January 2023 to September 2023, capturing both winter and summer seasonal variability in hydrodynamic and stratification processes. The Delft3D model, configured with a horizontal resolution of 100 meters and 30 vertical layers, was initialized using a hybrid approach, with water level and velocity data taken from the Copernicus model. The bathymetry used in the model was obtained from EMODnet. The model was set up with an open boundary on the western side, where Riemann invariants were applied to define flow conditions. To obtain a proper simulation of stratification patterns and vertical profiles of salinity and temperature, in-situ measurements provided by RV TÜBİTAK MARMARA are used to define the corresponding boundary condition: interpolated salinity and temperature profiles were imposed, based on seasonal data for January, April, and August. The model was forced with hourly wind and surface heat flux data obtained from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset, providing realistic atmospheric forcing throughout the simulation period.

Delft3D was calibrated using water surface elevation data from the Copernicus model as shown in Figure 1. The results are compared with Copernicus model outputs and seasonally measured in-situ data on salinity and temperature showing that Delft3D more accurately captured the halocline and thermocline structures, closely matching the measured data, outperforming the Copernicus model in representing vertical flow stratification.

Figure 1. Water level comparison between Delft3D and Copernicus

Keywords: hydrodynamic modelling, stratification; halocline, circulation, pycnocline, Delft3D